

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

PEACEKEEPING OPERATIONS TRAINING AS A COOPERATION BETWEEN BRAZIL AND SWEDEN

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ABSTRACT

The end of the Cold War (1991) diversified the conflicts around the world, increasing the quantity and complexity of the United Nations (UN) Peacekeeping Missions. In this sense, the 2000s began with a demand for new or more in-depth training in this type of operation. Sweden is a country with a long history of participation in Peacekeeping Missions, and Brazil, by taking command of the United Nations Stabilization Mission in Haiti (MINUSTAH), in 2004, increased its experience with peacekeeping abroad, being increasingly associated with the theme and expanding its international projection. Based on documents from the Brazilian Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MRE), therefore, this policy brief analyses Sweden's offer of Peacekeeping Missions training to Brazil in the 21st century, representing an area of bilateral cooperation.

BACKGROUND

If the Cold War (1945 - 1991) was a period marked by ideological, economic, and military disputes between the United States of America and the then Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR), the decade following its end was marked by new conflicts both in their essence and in the type of actors involved. Ethnic-religious, political, and territorial issues were enhanced, and no longer predominantly between states, but between local peoples, with regional repercussions. In this context, with the United Nations Organization (UNO) being the largest organization in the international system, founded at the end of World War II (1945) with the primary purpose of "maintaining international peace and security" (1), there has been a quantitative and qualitative evolution of its Peacekeeping Missions.

Sweden, like Brazil, has participated since the beginning of this type of UN mission (United Nations Truce Supervision Organization - UNTSO, for the First Arab-Israeli War, in 1948), with the particularity of sending female personnel and focusing on Africa and Eurasia. Brazil, in turn, has participated in more than 50 operations up to now, and stands out for its command of the United Nations Stabilization Mission in Haiti (MINUSTAH), which took place between 2004 and 2017, and of the Maritime Task Force of the United Nations Interim Force in Lebanon (FTM-UNIFIL), between 2011 and 2020 (2). Bilaterally, however, in addition to the tradition of non-involvement in armed conflicts (before the supply of armaments for the current war in Ukraine and the request for entry into the North Atlantic Treaty Organization - NATO, Sweden lived two centuries of neutrality), other areas bring the relations between Brazil and Sweden closer.

Throughout the 20th century, firstly, several Swedish companies settled in Brazil, which culminated in the signing of the "Agreement for Economic, Industrial and Technological Cooperation" (1989) between the two governments, making São Paulo, Brazil's largest city and financial capital, the second largest city with Swedish industry in the country, after Gothenburg. In Brazil as a whole, there are about 220 companies from Sweden, which, with the turn to the 21st century, had the Brazilian ethanol and the growing issue of sustainability in the energy sector as a trade highlight (3). Finally, in the military segment, in 2014, the Brazilian Air Force (FAB) purchased 36 Gripen E/F fighter (now, 40 already authorized) from Saab, Sweden's leading military defence and civil security company. Thus, Brazil and Sweden consolidated their military partnership, but interactions between their Armed Forces were already occurring, mainly for Peacekeeping Missions training.

RESULTS

From documentary research (2009 - current) in the Brazilian Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MRE) Archives, it was found the following list of Peacekeeping Mission training invitations by Sweden to Brazil:

Framework – Invitations of Peacekeeping Training from Sweden Brazil (2009 – current)

Year	Course	Institution
2009	Training for officers at UN, multinational bodies and international contingents in charge of peacekeeping operations	Nordic Coordinated Arrangement for Military Peace Support – NORDCAPS
	Civil Military Relations	Swedish Armed Forces International Centre – SWEDINT
2010	United Nations Police Officer	SWEDINT
2010	“International Crisis Management” for governmental and non-governmental bodies, mainly for Peacekeeping Operations	Swedish National Defence College
2010	Genderforce in the field	SWEDINT
2010	United Nations Staff Officer Course – UNSOC ⁱⁱ	UNO
2014	Course in English for multinational spaces of work, like Peacekeeping Missions	Swedish Armed Forces - SAF

Source: The author based on the Brazilian Ministry of Foreign Affairs Archives (4).

In addition, in 2018 and 2022, Brazil participated as a remote base in the Viking Exercise, being its strategic point in South America. Exercise Viking is the largest simulation in preparation for Peacekeeping Missions, organized by the Swedish Ministry of Defense, mainly, but with the support of the UN itself, the United States Department of Defense (DoD), NATO and the European Union/EU. Brazil's participation included the three Armed Forces (Army, Navy, and the Air Force), under the Brazilian Joint Center for Peace Operations/CCOPAB (5).

CONCLUSION

The chronology of Peacekeeping Mission training offered by Sweden to Brazil is concentrated until 2010, when the country was still implementing MINUSTAH as planned, with success in the stabilization process. Even after its closure, the Mission remains a reference, as does Brazil's participation in operations of this nature. However, in that year, there was a turning point: Haiti was devastated by an earthquake, which caused Brazil's presence there to focus primarily on humanitarian aid.

Since then, despite the last two editions of the Viking Exercise, the Swedish invitations to train for Peacekeeping Missions have been reduced. During this period, Brazil was not only in MINUSTAH until 2017, but also, in 2011, began its mandate in the Command of the FTM-UNIFIL, the world's only peacekeeping force with an eminently maritime component. And, in 2014, Brazil made the largest purchase in Saab's history with the Gripen fighter jets, which allowed both governments to express interest in deepening and expanding the partnership in the defence sectorⁱⁱⁱ.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Peacekeeping mission training has a two-way potential regarding international cooperation: the existence of relations with a particular country(ies) favors a greater offer, and the training itself contributes to the deepening of ties. In the Defence Cooperation Agreement (2014), for example, which is the largest in the sector between the governments of Brazil and Sweden, it states as one of the objectives, right in article 1, "to share knowledge and experience acquired in operations of the Armed Forces, including international peacekeeping operations, as well as in the use of national and foreign military equipment" (6).

Similarly, for Brazil's Military Attachment in Sweden, training for Peace Missions is one of the official points of common interest between the two countries (7). Therefore, in addition to capacity building, the interagency dynamic that occurs in Peacekeeping Missions training should be encouraged by both Brazil and Sweden, aiming to maintain bilateral international cooperation.

REFERENCES

- (1) United Nations (2023). About us. Available in: <https://www.un.org/en/>.
- (2) Ambinder, C. Antunes, A. (2021). Brazil and Sweden in Peacekeeping Missions and the Viking Exercise 2022. InterAgency Institute. Available at: https://zenodo.org/record/5716103#.Y9_nD3bMLrc.
- (3) Ministry of Foreign Affairs (2023). Sweden. Available at: <https://www.gov.br/mre/pt-br/assuntos/portal-consular/reparticoes-consulares-do-brasil/regiao/suecia/suecia>.
- (4) _____. (2023). Archives. Brasília.
- (5) Ambinder, C. Antunes, A. (2021). Brazil and Sweden in Peacekeeping Missions and the Viking Exercise 2022. InterAgency Institute. Available at: https://zenodo.org/record/5716103#.Y9_nD3bMLrc.
- (6) Brazil (2014). Framework Agreement between the Government of the Federative Republic of Brazil and the Kingdom of Sweden on Cooperation in Defence Matters. Available at: http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2015-2018/2018/decreto/d9284.htm.
- (7) Fonseca, N. (2022). Interview given to Carolina Ambinder. Estocolmo. Fev. 2022.

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ⁱⁱ Held through the Technical Reserve of the Brazilian Navy's (MB) Program for Courses and Internships Abroad (PCEExt), involving the General Command of the Marine Corps (CGCFN) and the Naval Operations Command (ComOpNav) - MB Administrative Bulletin.

ⁱⁱⁱ Proof of this expansion interest on the part of Sweden is Saab's offer of Mine Countermeasures Vessels for the Brazilian Navy, which includes training at Swedish Navy facilities.